

POLICY IMPLICATIONS OF GREEN PRODUCT DESIGN

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Abstract—The design of products is strongly influenced by Federal and State environmental regulations. It is important that these regulations be shaped to encourage, rather than inhibit, green design approaches. Policies to encourage green design should have three characteristics: the problem to be addressed should be clearly defined; regulations should provide maximum flexibility to the designer, and they should promote a "systems" approach to design. This paper explores these criteria further and illustrates them with current examples.

INTRODUCTION

Product design provides a unique point of leverage to address environmental problems. Design is the stage where decisions are made regarding the types of resources and manufacturing processes to be used, and these processes ultimately determine the characteristics of waste streams. By giving designers incentives to consider the environmental impacts of their choices, policymakers can address environmental problems that arise throughout the product life cycle, from the extraction of raw materials to final disposal.

This paper explores how policymakers can shape environmental policies that encourage, rather than inhibit, green design practices. It is based on the recent Office of Technology Assessment report Green Products by Design: Choices for a Cleaner Environment (OTA-E-541, Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, October, 1992).

THE GOALS OF GREEN DESIGN

Government regulations typically influence the design process by imposing external constraints, for example, compliance by automobile designers with Corporate Average Fuel Economy Standards, or with emission standards under the Clean Air Act. OTA uses the phrase "green design" to mean something qualitatively different: a design process in which environmental attributes are treated as design objectives, rather than as constraints.

In OTA's formulation, green design involves two general goals: waste prevention and better materials management (Fig. 1). Waste prevention refers to activities by manufacturers and consumers that avoid the generation of waste in the first place. Examples include using less material to perform the same function ("light-weighting") or designing durable products so that faulty or obsolete components can be readily replaced, thus extending the product's service life. Better materials management refers to activities that allow product components or materials to be recovered and re-used in their highest value-added application. Examples include designing products that can be readily disassembled into constituent materials, or using materials that can be recycled together without the need for separation. These goals should be viewed as complementary: while designers may reduce the quantity of resources used and wastes generated, products and waste streams will still exist and have to be managed.

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Fig. 1. How Design Affects Materials Flows

In general, materials flow through the economy in one direction only—from raw materials toward eventual disposal as industrial or municipal waste (top). By making changes in a product's design, overall environmental impact can be reduced (bottom). Green design emphasizes efficient use of materials and energy, reduction of waste toxicity, and reuse and recycling of materials.

U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, *Green Products by Design: Choices for a Cleaner Environment*, OTA-E-541 (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, October 1992).

PRODUCT DESIGN AND THE ENVIRONMENT

The idea of green design seems simple, but there is no rigid formula or decision hierarchy for implementing it. One reason is that what is "green" depends strongly on context. While some environmental design objectives are sufficiently compelling to apply to many different products (e.g., avoiding the use of CFCs), in general OTA expects that green choices will only become clear with respect to specific classes of products or production networks. What constitutes green design may depend on such factors as: the length of product life; product performance, safety, and reliability; toxicity of constituents and available substitutes; available waste management technologies; and local conditions under which the product is used and disposed.

Environmental Tradeoffs

With technologies available to create new materials and to combine conventional materials in new ways, designers are faced with more choices than ever before. Increasingly, these choices involve environmental dilemmas. Tradeoffs may be required, not only between traditional and environmental objectives, but even among environmental objectives themselves: e.g., waste prevention versus recyclability.

As an illustration, consider the cross section of a modern snack chip bag depicted schematically in Fig. 2. The combination of nine extremely thin layers using many different materials produces a lightweight package that meets a variety of needs (e.g., preserving freshness, indicating tampering, and providing product information). The use of

Fig. 2. Cross-Section of a Snack Chip Bag

This cross-section of a snack chip bag illustrates the complexity of modern packaging. The bag is approximately 0.002 inches thick, and consists of nine different layers, each with a specific function. While such complexity can inhibit recycling efforts, it also can reduce the overall weight of the bag, and keep food fresher, thus providing waste prevention benefits.

SOURCE: Council on Plastics and Packaging in the Environment.

so many disparate materials effectively inhibits recycling. On the other hand, the package has waste prevention attributes; it is much lighter than an equivalent package made of a single material, and provides a longer shelf life, resulting in less food wastage. Even this relatively simple product demonstrates the difficulties of measuring green design.

Similar tradeoffs may occur between other environmental attributes, such as energy efficiency and toxicity. For example, energy-efficient compact fluorescent bulbs contain mercury, and toxic chemicals are required to manufacture photovoltaic cells. In general, every design will have its own set of environmental pluses and minuses. This suggests that government policies should be flexible enough to accommodate such tradeoffs.

Product-Oriented vs. System-Oriented Design

From an environmental point of view, it is simplistic to consider the impact of a product is isolation from the production and consumption system in which it functions. Is a computer, for example, a green product? Thanks to EPA's Energy Star program and studies conducted by the Microelectronics and Computer Corporation (MCC), it is becoming greener. But considered on its own, the manufacture of a computer requires large volumes of hazardous chemicals and solvents, and heavy metals used in solder, wiring, and display screens are a significant contributor to the heavy metal content of municipal solid waste.

Considered as part of a larger system, though, the same computer could be used to increase the efficiency of a manufacturing process, thus avoiding the use of many tons of raw materials and the generation of many tons of wastes. From this perspective, the computer is an enabling technology that reduces the environmental impacts of the production system as a whole.

This illustrates an important OTA finding: green design is likely to have its largest impact in the context of changing the overall systems ("industrial ecology") in which products are manufactured, used, and disposed, rather than in changing the composition of products per se. For instance, designing lighter fast food packaging is well and good; but 80 percent of the waste from a typical fast food restaurant is generated *behind the counter*, where consumers never see it. Addressing this larger problem requires that designers establish cooperative relationships with their suppliers and waste management providers in order to manage materials flows in an environmentally sound way.

There may appear to be few incentives for industry to consider such dramatic changes in existing production networks. After all, longstanding relationships among manufacturers and suppliers may have to change, and millions of dollars may be invested in the existing infrastructure for production and distribution. In any case, such changes are not generally within the purview of product designers. Indeed, a systems design approach implies the elevation of the product design function to the level of strategic business planning, and a shift in perception by top management in which environmental quality is viewed not as a cost, but as a strategic business opportunity.

But changes of comparable magnitude are already underway. Many manufacturers are rethinking their business relationships with suppliers and customers in order to implement Total Quality Management and Concurrent Engineering programs. New government regulations in Europe that give manufacturers responsibility for the environmental fate of their products are also encouraging this approach. For example, Germany's proposed law requiring automakers to take back and recycle automobiles has stimulated the German auto industry to develop new cooperative strategies for auto design, manufacture, disassembly, and recycling. This systems-oriented design approach is completely different from one in which an individual designer might try to reduce the weight of a fender or bumper by 10 percent (product-oriented approach).

THE EMERGENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL PRODUCT POLICY

With technologies available to create new materials and to combine conventional materials in new ways, designers are faced with more choices than ever before. The development of environmental policies that are flexible enough to accommodate these choices and the complex impacts of design on the environment is a considerable challenge. Nevertheless, policies with great impact on design are evolving rapidly at Federal, State, and international levels.

Federal Statutes

Whereas most environmental statutes such as the Clean Air Act, Clean Water Act, and Resource Conservation and Recovery Act focus on the "back end" of industrial processes--i.e., releases of pollutants to the environment, there is a growing tendency around the world to shift the focus of environmental policy more toward the "front end"--putting the emphasis on the materials inputs to industrial processes and the environmentally conscious design of products. In the United States, there is no better example of this emerging "environmental product policy" than the Congressional debate over the reauthorization of RCRA.

The Resource Conservation and Recovery Act is the Nation's principal statute dealing with solid waste. Despite its name, RCRA has not historically addressed either resource conservation or recovery. Instead, it has been concerned chiefly with the treatment, storage, and disposal of so-called "hazardous" industrial waste, and to a lesser extent, with municipal solid waste. But this emphasis began to change with the debate over the reauthorization of RCRA, whose formal authorization expired at the end of Fiscal Year 1988. Numerous proposals have been made that would result in regulations on the environmental attributes of products and chemical use; for example:

- o Requiring products to contain a certain percentage of recycled content
- o Developing standards for environmental advertising and product labels
- o Establishing green criteria for government procurement of products
- o Expanding industry reporting requirements on its use of chemicals
- o Requiring industry to reduce its use of "toxic" chemicals

This shift of policy emphasis to the front end of the manufacturing process has enormous implications for product design. Whereas Federal policy has long been concerned with protecting the environment from industrial waste streams, the choice of what materials should be used in products has largely been a private sector decision. The emergence of environmental product policy implies government intrusion into areas that have traditionally been considered the province of private industry.

RCRA reauthorization did not pass in the 102nd Congress, and so it remains on the Congressional agenda in the 103rd. The proposals mentioned above, and others like them, will once again be part of the debate. As the reauthorization bills make their way through the House and Senate, there will be numerous opportunities for companies and trade associations to make their voices heard on these issues.

State Laws

In many cases, State and local governments are taking the lead in enacting policies aimed at reducing the environmental impacts of products. These measures include mandatory industry plans to reduce the use of toxic chemicals, requirements for industry disclosure of the use of hazardous chemicals in products, and creation of standard definitions for advertisers' use of environmental terms such as "recycled." States have also enacted some targeted product control measures such as recycled content requirements for newspaper, bans and taxes on specific packages, mandated manufacturer take-back of batteries, and tax incentives for recycling. In some cases, these laws regulate products and processes more strictly than do Federal laws. Notable examples are California's regulations on auto emissions, permissible volatile organic compound content of products, and labeling requirements for products containing carcinogens and reproductive toxics.

The lack of uniform Federal environmental standards for products is alarming to industry, which fears having to satisfy different regulations in each State. For example, there are 35 different State definitions of the term "hazardous." This prospect is especially of concern for products that are distributed through national networks. Companies are faced with the choice of redesigning products to meet the most stringent State requirement, or changing their distribution systems. The question of when Federal intervention is desirable to harmonize divergent State regulations, and when it is inappropriate, will have to be resolved by Congress and the courts.

International Developments

The integration of product policy into environmental policy and the role of design in making products more friendly to the environment are areas of considerable policy ferment around the world. Twenty-two of the major industrialized countries either have a national eco-labeling program for products, or will have one soon. There are a growing number of product control policies in effect, ranging from outright bans on materials to economic instruments such as product taxes.

The political atmosphere surrounding waste management in Europe has forced drastic policy measures such as Germany's Packaging Waste Law. This law has set the tone for a common policy theme emerging in several European countries: the idea of giving manufacturers responsibility for recovering and recycling their products at the end of their useful life. Manufacturer take-back requirements have intuitive appeal because they give designers direct incentives to consider how the product will be recovered and recycled, thus "closing the loop" among design, manufacturing, and waste management.

The idea of shifting responsibility for life-cycle management of products to manufacturers can be expected to have a growing appeal in the United States as well, particularly given that U.S. cities are collecting recyclable materials at a rate much faster than they are being used. Those U.S.-based multinational firms with subsidiaries in Europe are already changing their design thinking in response to the emerging European environmental product policies. Many U.S. manufacturers, especially those of durable goods, feel that similar legislation is inevitable in the United States in a few years.

Many policy instruments, including both regulatory and market-based incentives, are available to address the environmental problems associated with the flow of goods and materials through the economy. These instruments can be applied at various stages of the product life cycle, from the extraction of raw materials to final disposal. An analysis of the design impacts of these options is beyond the scope of this paper. However, OTA offers three guiding principles that policymakers should consider in order to encourage, rather than inhibit, green design.

Principle 1: Identify the Root Problem and Define It Clearly.

One of the biggest challenges in selecting a policy strategy is clearly defining the problem to be addressed. In the absence of a clearly defined problem, it becomes easy to confuse means and ends. Proxies for environmental quality, such as recycling, can come to be perceived as ends in themselves, rather than as one of several strategies for reducing the problem of solid waste. By mandating that products and packaging contain a minimum recycled content, for instance, Congress would certainly encourage product designers to use secondary materials in packaging; but this would not necessarily result in less waste overall. Perversely, this could even lead to more waste, especially if designs featuring waste prevention are thereby discouraged. If the objective is to reduce the amount of solid waste generated, MSW policies and government procurement programs should make allowances for product designs that feature waste prevention.

Defining the problem properly must entail some consideration of environmental risks. OTA finds that policymakers currently lack critical information on how materials flow through the economy and about the relative risks of different materials and products. For example, the RCRA reauthorization debate has focused on heavy metals contained in plastic packaging, even though this source

contributes only 4 to 7 percent of heavy metals in landfills and incinerators. Without research to develop information on materials flows and relative risks, resources are likely to be directed toward the most visible problems, rather than those that pose the greatest environmental risks.

Principle 2: Give Designers the Maximum Flexibility That Is Consistent with Solving the Problem.

Materials technology options are proliferating rapidly, and product impacts on the environment are nearly always multidimensional. Policies should be crafted to give designers as much flexibility as possible to find the best solutions, within a framework that protects human health and the environment. Rigid Federal mandates that impose a predetermined design solution (such as bans on the use of certain materials) are likely to be inefficient, and should be avoided if possible.

Flexibility can be achieved through a variety of means, including flexible regulations, economic instruments, and voluntary agreements. Perhaps the greatest administrative flexibility can be achieved through voluntary agreements. Such agreements are easier and faster to implement than legislation and regulations, and may be attractive to industry because it has more control over the goals and timetables. For example, reaching a voluntary agreement with manufacturers to reduce packaging waste by 10 percent over one year is likely to be cheaper for both government and industry than a regulation requiring every package to be 10 percent lighter or contain 10 percent recycled content. Voluntary agreements with industry are being used more extensively in Europe, and examples in the United States include EPA's 33/50 Program and Green Lights Program.

Market-based policy instruments will generally provide a more flexible environment for product design than regulations, because designers are free to make choices based on minimizing overall costs. Economic instruments may be used in place of regulations or as a supplement to make their implementation more flexible and cost effective. For example, a regulation requiring a fixed percentage of recycled content in products may be implemented more cost effectively by establishing a tradable recycling credit mechanism to encourage those manufacturers who can incorporate recovered materials most cheaply to do so.

One tradeoff for increasing policy flexibility is likely to be increased costs of policy monitoring and enforcement. For example, verifying compliance with a ban requires less information than verifying compliance with voluntary agreements or flexible regulations. For this approach to work, the cost of demonstrating compliance will probably have to be borne by industry.

Principle 3: Encourage a Systems Approach to Green Design.

If policymakers focus exclusively on addressing the environmental attributes of products, as opposed to the systems in which products are manufactured, used, and disposed, they are likely to miss the biggest opportunities for green design.

A systems-oriented design approach can be encouraged either directly through regulation, or indirectly through economic incentives. Recycled content regulations or manufacturer take-back requirements are examples of regulatory coupling between the manufacturing and waste management stages of a product's life cycle. However, this approach may not be appropriate for all products. For example, take-back regulations may be more appropriate for high-value, durable goods than for non-durable or disposable goods.

An alternative approach is to use economic instruments, such as environmental taxes, deposit refund systems, or tradable permits to internalize the costs of environmental services. This approach would rely on market forces to sort out what new inter firm relationships make sense economically, while giving designers the flexibility to design products with the best combination of cost, performance, and least environmental impact. For example, a substantial tax on energy consumption would have a dramatic impact on the systems by which products are manufactured, distributed, and disposed, because fuels are consumed at every stage of the product life cycle.

CONCLUSION

This is a formative period for the development of environmental product policies at the State, Federal, and international levels. Much depends on shaping policies that target the right problems and give designers the flexibility to find innovative, environmentally sound solutions. In reauthorizing RCRA and other environmental laws, Congress has an opportunity to refocus attention and resources on the key problems associated with present materials flows. If it frames the objective in terms of reducing the generation of wastes, especially those that pose the greatest risks, it will encourage the design of products that use resources efficiently and waste management programs that are cost-effective. If, on the other hand, it frames the objective strictly in terms of increased recycling rates, and if it fails to distinguish high-risk waste streams from low-risk waste streams, it may encourage less efficient product designs and less efficient waste management programs.